

ReBioCycle objectives

- Improve circularity and resource efficiency via practical application of the circular bioeconomy concept in the biobased and biodegradable plastics value chain.
- Scale up effective sorting and recycling schemes for biobased and biodegradable plastic materials.
- Increase the recycled content in new products from biobased and biodegradable plastics.
- Improve the environmental performance across the value chain against fossil or biobased benchmarks.
- Achieve better social acceptance of circular biobased solutions and products.

Biobased biodegradable plastics can be kept in the cycle for as long as possible through innovative recycling technologies and end-of-life biobased biodegradable plastics can be part of the circular bioeconomy.

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Project duration
4 years
1 October 2024 –
30 September 2028

www.rebiocycle.eu

ReBioCycle has received funding from the Circular Bio-based Joint Undertaking (JU) and its members under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101156032. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme and the Bio-based Industries Consortium.

A new European blueprint for circular bioplastics upcycling solutions

ReBioCycle solutions

ReBioCycle provides a **portfolio of bioplastic sorting and recycling technologies across three complementary, waste-processor-centric hubs**. These hubs operate at a demonstration scale in real operational environments to enable the effective and efficient recycling of **three types of bioplastics (PLA, PHA, and composites)**. The project aims to achieve a higher impact by producing recycled polymers of the same or superior grade and other higher-value applications. The three hubs are located in **Spain, Italy, and the Netherlands**.

- ReBioCycle will **test and scale existing and new technologies** for mechanical, chemical and biological recycling of biobased biodegradable plastics.
- ReBioCycle will **scale to pilot and demonstration scale** to advance the technology readiness level of these technologies to accelerate their implementation in the marketplace.

ReBioCycle's three steps approach

Dutch HUB

Italian HUB

Spanish HUB

Horizontal Partners:

